

DEVELOPMENT OF A CYCLIC TEST METHOD FOR ULTRA-FAST ROTATING FLYWHEELS MADE OF CFRP AND IMPROVEMENT OF THEIR FATIGUE STRENGTH BY MATRIX MODIFICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Flywheels made of carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) are recently under development for the application in energy storage systems. As they undergo several periods of deceleration and acceleration their fatigue resistance is the main design objective. This study presents a cyclic test method that can be used to estimate the lifetime performance of CFRP-tubes manufactured by winding technology. This test method is designed to assess the effectivity of different matrix modifications that aim for an augmented lifetime. Three modified matrix systems have been identified as most promising: two systems that are modified with core-shell rubber (CSR) particles and one system with carbon nanotubes (CNT). The developed test methods as well as comparison of the mechanical and thermal properties between the reference system and the three modified systems are summarized in the present paper.

The requirements on the cyclic test methods are specified under manufacturing considerations and on the basis of a finite element study of the flywheel component. The consideration of these requirements leads to the choice of an adaption of the split-disk method to cyclic loading conditions. The paper then provides information on specimen preparation and describes the test set-up. The results of the quasi-static split-disk test are discussed manifesting the necessity of considering a size-effect for the calculation of the static strength in fibre direction. During cyclic loading the stiffness degradation is monitored indicating the occurrence of different damaging mechanisms and resulting damages, such as delamination and inter-fibre failure, before the final failure. The so far conducted fatigue tests suggest that by adapting the split-disk method to cyclic loading conditions reproducible results can be obtained. A frank discussion of the herein studied test method reveals critical points that still need closer investigation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Flywheels made of CFRP are suitable for the application in short-term energy storage systems. They can be used for the stabilization of energy grids or for the recovery of surplus energy charged before. Very high rotational speeds are mandatory for a maximum storage capacity given that the kinetic energy (E_{kin}) increases by a power of two of the angular velocity (ω):

$$E_{kin} = \frac{1}{2} I \omega^2 \quad (1)$$

where I is the moment of inertia and thus dependant on the mass. For each loading and unloading of the flywheel, the material of the component is subjected to high circumferential tensile stresses. Therefore a high cyclic strength under tensile mode is mandatory for the lifetime performance of the flywheel.

Recent studies [1-3] suggested the positive impact of matrix modifications on the fatigue performance of epoxy resins and carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resins (CF/EP). By incorporating CSR

nanoparticles into a CF/EP both the fracture toughness and the fatigue strength can be significantly increased [1]. Ozdemir et al. [2] found a remarkable toughening effect by introducing rubber particles into a CFRP composite. In [3] the addition of triblock copolymers into an epoxy resin led to an important gain of resistance to fatigue crack propagation. Therefore, in the presented study various matrix modifications were tested and characterized in order to augment the lifetime compared to a reference epoxy resin. The testing of the different matrix systems included the determination of the important mechanical properties as well as the characteristics influencing the workability.

A common test method for the assessment of the fatigue strength of rotating components is the spin test. The major disadvantages of the spin test for the present component are the extensive testing time and costs. Also, a monitoring of stiffness degradation and the development of damage in the CFRP structure during the test is not possible. To the author's knowledge, alternative test methods for the lifetime assessment of hoop wound cylinders have not yet been studied. For the determination of the quasi-static mechanical properties of hoop wound cylinders two test methods are state of the art: the split-disk test and the method for internal pressure testing. A recent publication [4] dealt with the comparison of these methods and came to the conclusion that the split-disk method, adapted by means of finite element simulation, provides reliable results for the strength in fibre direction whereas values are underestimated by internal pressure testing.

The objective of this study is the development of a test method that can adequately replace a spin test for the assessment of the fatigue performance of a flywheel. The present study focuses on the lifetime assessment of the tube made of CF/EP and on the improvement of the fatigue resistance of the laminate by matrix modification. The other components of the flywheel are not further investigated.

2 MATRIX MODIFICATION

To augment the lifetime of the flywheel the reference resin system was modified in order to improve its ductility. The flywheel component manufacturing is done by filament winding and thus requires a low viscosity of the matrix system for a proper fibre impregnation. Therefore, a crucial parameter for the workability is to only alter the viscosity of the resin systems by varying its composition within narrow boundaries. In the presented study, in addition to the verification of the workability of the matrix modification the mechanical, fracture mechanical, viscoelastic and thermal properties of the modified resin systems were systematically examined. Subsequently, the results were compared to an anhydride cured cycloaliphatic reference epoxy system. As the matrix material in the flywheel is subjected to high tensile strains caused by the widening of the component under centrifugal forces, a main focus was placed on the ultimate strain for the assessment of the efficiency of the modification.

Figure 1: Mechanical and thermal properties of various resin systems for flywheel application

To increase the ultimate strain of the matrix system various approaches were pursued, e.g. making use of additional micromechanical mechanisms introduced into the brittle epoxy system by a particulate or chemical modification. During this extensive modifier screening three systems were identified as the most promising ones, namely an elevated ultimate strain and still meeting the other requirements. The first system, a core-shell rubber (CSR) toughened aromatic epoxy system, showed a tremendously increased ultimate strain due to micro-crack pinning effects and plastic void growth of the matrix material. However, the glass transition temperature was reduced, but still meeting the requirements. A second approach was the synergistic reduction of the cross-link density and the introduction of CSR particles into the reference system. This doubled the ultimate strain with respect to the reference system. Finally, functionalized carbon nanotubes (CNT) were mechanically dispersed via a three-roll calendar into the reference system, which were found to be beneficial for improving the mechanical properties as well as the fracture toughness. The analysed properties of the selected resin systems are presented in figure 1.

3 DEVELOPMENT OF A CYCLIC TEST METHOD

The main objective of this study is the development of a test method that can adequately replace a spin test for a lifetime assessment of a flywheel. The herein studied flywheel is made of a commercial CF/EP and consists of hoop-wound and helical-wound layers. For the application in ultra-fast rotating flywheels the main focus is placed on a high performance material rather than on a lightweight construction. Contrarily to lightweight construction objectives, the mass linearly augments the rotational energy and thus the storage capacity. In order to obtain a high strength the layers possess a very high fibre volume ratio (FVR). A manufacturing process that allows high FVR's is the winding technology. This is particularly true for circumferential bodies. By winding plane sheets, however, only a significantly lower FVR can be reached. Therefore and in order to apply the same manufacturing process for the specimens as for the prototype, it was searched for a testing method that uses a circumferential specimen produced by winding technology.

By means of a finite element analysis the stress state of the flywheel due to residual stresses, acceleration and deceleration as well as high rotational speed was studied. Whereas the helical-wound layers provide the longitudinal stiffness to prevent resonance in the flexural mode, the hoop-wound layers carry the circumferential load resulting of the centrifugal force. Compared to the stresses caused by the centrifugal force the residual stresses due to manufacturing and the stresses caused by acceleration and deceleration can be neglected.

The centrifugal force leads to tensile stresses in fibre direction in the hoop-wound layers. These circumferential stresses result in tensile stresses perpendicular to the fibre direction as well as shear stresses in the helical layers. Furthermore, the differing stiffness in helical and hoop layers causes tensile stresses perpendicular to the fibre direction in the hoop layers. To summarize, in the load carrying layers the material stressing effort due to fibre and inter-fibre-failure is 0.5 and 0.3 respectively. Given the fact that the fatigue resistance against inter-fibre failure decreases more rapidly than the resistance against fibre failure, it can be stated that the mode of failure depends on the applied stress-level. Therefore, an appropriate test specimen has to consist of helical as well as hoop-wound layers to reproduce the decisive stress state.

Under static loading the split-disk method is a valid test method for the comparison of hoop-wound laminates. One characteristic of this method is the imposed bending moment at the split leading to a superposition with the tensile circumferential stress. This is the main reason for the rare application of this test method in the past. In the present study the bending of the specimen in the split is even a desirable effect, given the fact that the circumferential tensile stresses due to a centrifugal force increase from the inside to the outside of a tube. This effect is even more pronounced in thick laminates as it is the case in the present study. Furthermore, a more recent study on glass-fibre and carbon-fibre reinforced hoop wound cylinders showed that by adapting the experimental results via a finite element analysis, the strength and even stiffness of a unidirectional laminate can be obtained [4]. The main objective of the present study is the comparison of different matrix systems on the basis of their fatigue performance in a laminate; therefore an adapted cyclic split-disk-test seems the adequate instrument.

4 TEST SET-UP

The ASTM-standard D 2290 covers the regulation for the split-disk-method under quasi-static loading and thus can be applied for the determination of the apparent hoop tensile strength of fibre-reinforced plastic tubes [5]. The test fixture is to be constructed in a manner that the influence of the bending moment is minimized meaning an initial split as small as possible.

4.1 Specimens

The standard offers two different types of specimens: a ring with two reduced cross-sections located 180° apart, which is used for testing circumferentially fibre-reinforced thermosetting resins and a specimen with a full cross-section. A finite element study with the chosen laminate lay-up proves that in the reduced cross-section inter-fibre failure occurs before fibre-failure. Consequently, the circumferential strength cannot be determined by using a specimen with a reduced cross-section, which has also been the finding for unidirectional reinforced tubes [4]. Therefore, a test set-up with full cross-section specimens is chosen for the present study.

For the specimen preparation a tube is wound on a mandrel with a diameter of 146 mm. The laminate is composed of helical and hoop layers with an adapted ratio to the lay-up of the flywheel resulting in a laminate thickness of 3.5 mm. Compared to other split-disk-tests, this high thickness, however, results in an elevated aspect ratio thus causing a higher impact of the bending moment [6].

The specimens are then cut with a rotating diamond saw blade in rings with a width of 7 mm. To remove cutting marks, which can have a significant impact on the fatigue strength, the rings are then wet-sanded and polished.

Considering the great influence of the thickness of the hoop layer on the resulting stress distribution, the thickness and fibre-volume content is determined by using microscopy. Figure 2 presents two microscopic scans of the same specimen illustrating the considerable variation of thickness of the hoop layer complicating an exact assessment of the resulting stresses. Thus it can be stated that the specimen thickness cannot be measured manually, but needs to be determined with microscopic scans.

Figure 2: Microscopic scans of one specimen

4.2 Set-up

The specimen is mounted on two disks and subsequently fixed at the top and the bottom to avoid a rotation during the cyclic testing (see fig. 3a). An exact parallel alignment of the specimen with regard to the disks is mandatory in order to avoid an unintentional bending. The disks are then fixed with bolts in two brackets that can be pulled apart. After mounting the disks it has to be ensured, that the two bolts are perfectly aligned to ensure a constant position of the specimen during the test. Additionally, to observe an unintentional rotation of the ring and thus detect invalid test results pictures are taken at regular intervals.

To capture possible stiffness degradation an inductive displacement transducer is attached to the two brackets. The temperature rise of the specimen due to external and internal friction is monitored by a thermocouple and a thermal camera focused on the split.

Prior to the cyclic split-disk tests, quasi-static tests were conducted. The tests were performed under displacement control with a velocity of 2.0 mm/min. The cyclic tests are performed under force control with a loading frequency of 1 Hz and a stress ratio of $R = 0.1$. Both tests are conducted at a servo-hydraulic testing machine.

Figure 3: a) Fixture at the bottom of the ring b) Test set-up

5 RESULTS

5.1 Quasi-static tests

A finite element model of the quasi-static tests was used to account for the influence of the resulting bending moment on the calculated strength. Under the ultimate load the maximum stress in fibre direction was calculated to $R_{t,II} = 3260$ MPa. Additionally, the mean strength was calculated according to the standard to $R_{t,II} = 2460$ MPa, only taking hoop layers into account. It can be stated that the influence of the bending moment on the calculated strength is significant. This is due to the low aspect ratio (w/t) of the specimen.

In the present study, the fact that the highly stressed volume is very small cannot be neglected and thus size effects have to be considered when estimating the effective strength via the finite element method. This effect is not covered by present study. Thus for the estimation of the fatigue strength, the proceeding according to the standard is adopted which is determination of the mean by the applied force divided by the loaded cross section.

5.2 Cyclic tests

Figure 4 a) shows the development of the ratio between force and displacement, herein referred to as stiffness evolution, during a cyclic split-disk test. The graph shows an increasing stiffness up to 10^5 cycles. After a short plateau, a steep drop can be observed followed by almost constant stiffness degradation until final rupture.

To the knowledge of the authors, a stiffness increase up to 10^5 cycles has not yet been stated in the literature. The only, but not yet validated, explanation for this phenomenon is the constant alignment of the fibres in circumferential direction leading to an increasing stiffness. The interpretation of stiffness degradation during cyclic loading allows drawing conclusions on the development of damage. For instance, a steep drop of the stiffness can indicate the occurrence of a damage mechanism such as delamination or fibre fracture. By the combination of stiffness degradation monitoring and imaging techniques such as micro-computed tomography (μ -CT) the damage mechanisms can be detected. Figure 4 b) shows a μ -CT scan of a specimen detail at the split. The specimen has been tested up to the point where a decreasing stiffness was observed. Two damage mechanisms can be detected: a delamination between helical and hoop layer and a radial crack in the hoop layer. It is not yet clear which damage mechanism developed first and caused the other one. Further tests can provide a more detailed insight into the damage mechanisms that lead to this stiffness evolution during the cyclic split-disk test.

Figure 4: a) Stiffness degradation during a cyclic split-disk test b) μ -CT scan after manually interrupted cyclic split-disk test

So far, the cyclic split-disk test has been conducted at different stress levels for the reference material. The test results are presented in Figure 5. It can be observed, that the scatter of the results is relatively small for the fatigue behaviour of CRFP. This suggests that the cyclic split-disk method is a valid test method for the comparison of different CFRP laminates with regard to their fatigue strength.

Figure 5: Test results of cyclic split-disk tests with specimens made of reference resin

6 CONCLUSIONS

The main focus of the present study was the development of a testing method to assess the lifetime performance of a flywheel made of CF/EP. Therefore, the well-established split-disk method was adapted to cyclic loading conditions. The small scatter in the test results lead to the conclusion that this test method provides reproducible fatigue data and thereby is much less time-consuming than the state-of-the-art spin test.

Furthermore, a matrix modification using CSR-particles and CNT's lead to significantly improved mechanical properties of the epoxy resin. Further cyclic split-disk tests on the laminate made of the modified resin will show the impact of the modification on the laminate fatigue properties. An analysis of the improved mechanical resin properties and the fatigue data will then allow identifying the for decisive resin properties for improved fatigue resistance.

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